

REIMAGINING THE COLLEGE STUDENTS' ADJUSTMENT, PERCEIVED STRESS AND THEIR SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING: INPUT FOR RESILIENCE IN SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT UPLIFT PROGRAM (RISE - UP)

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ABSTRACT

The transition from high school to college is pivotal for young adults, fostering growth and friendships while presenting mental health challenges. The UN's Sustainable Development Agenda targets health and education to improve student well-being during this period. A descriptive-correlational study surveyed 602 first-year college students using a survey questionnaire to assess adjustment, stress, and subjective well-being. Findings revealed significant adjustment issues related to academics, social life, and finances, affecting students' well-being. To support them, universities must implement resilience programs and prioritize mental health services, aligning with SDGs 3 and 4 for improved coping and educational quality.

Keywords: *college adjustment, perceived stress, resilience, subjective well-being*

INTRODUCTION

The transition from high school to college marks a distinct phase in a student's academic career. The phase denotes adjustment from a dependent to independent learner, from studying in a carefully supervised environment with a highly controlled

timetable to students learning to manage their own time and make decisions in a more adult and responsible manner. This transition appears stressful because students must cope with teasing and bullying, conflict with teachers or parents, competition or disagreements with peers, homework, tests and class presentations, and the transition from one school to another (Wu et al, 2021).

It is well established that all college students will experience difficult situations at some point in their educational career, both academic and social (Bruffaerts et al., 2018). Accordingly, college years of young adults demands them to be responsible concerning their health, school life and financial situation. Thus, college years are accepted as one of the most stressful periods as youths need to manage their own lives (Hoyt et al., 2021).

These issues can be compounding; mental health challenges present increased risk for academic failure and drop-out, especially during the first year in the university (Tasso et al., 2021). Resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, significant changes and disruptions to daily life were experienced by students. Elevated stress levels, and mental and physical health deterioration of the students are evident (Yang et al., 2021).

It was observable by Commission on Higher Education that in 2023, 41.16% students either temporarily leave college or drop out permanently (Chi, 2023). While several studies have underscored the impact of the pandemic on younger students, there is also evidence pointing to the health crisis' impact on tertiary education students.

Looking on the 2021 study by the University of the Philippines' Population Institute, it was estimated that around one in five Filipinos aged 15 to 24 years old — or 1.5 million in total — have considered ending their own life. Most or six in 10 did not reach out to anyone about their suicide ideation. While any college student is vulnerable to these stressors and low well - being, these concerns are amplified for members of minority groups (Kodish et al., 2022).

Identifying students at greatest risk provides opportunities to offer support, resources, and mental health services especially for educational institutions the students are enrolled in that reflects a commitment to fostering holistic development and aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). That resonates with SDG 4 (Quality Education), emphasizing the provision of inclusive and equitable quality education, and SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), addressing mental health awareness and stress management.

Consequently, more studies should be conducted to address this gap in research to help identify college students that may be disproportionately impacted by low adjustment, perceived high stress and low subjective well – being. From this, this research aims to evaluates the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being. The results of the study will be the basis for crafting a guidance program which intends to capacitate students to adapt well when facing adversity or stress. This could help students avoid if not, lessen the potential negative psychological effects of challenging experiences.

Research Questions

This study aims to examine the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being. The results of the study will be the basis for resilience in the school environment uplift program.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 gender and
 - 1.2 program/degree?
2. How is the college students' adjustment be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 academic adjustment;
 - 2.2 social adjustment;
 - 2.3 personal adjustment; and
 - 2.4 institutional adjustment?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the college students' adjustment when grouped according to:
 - 3.1 gender and
 - 3.2 program/degree?
4. How is the college students' perceived stress be described in terms of:
 - 4.1 academic-related stressor;
 - 4.2 time-related stressor;
 - 4.3 family-related stressor;
 - 4.4 financial-related stressor;
 - 4.5 intrapersonal-related stressor;
 - 4.6 interpersonal-related stressor;
 - 4.7 teacher-related stressor; and
 - 4.8 environmental-related stressor?
5. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the college students' perceived stress when grouped according to:
 - 5.1 gender and
 - 5.2 program/degree?
6. How is the college students' subjective well – being be described in terms of:
 - 6.1 satisfaction with academics;
 - 6.2 academic grit;
 - 6.3 school connectedness;
 - 6.4 academic self-efficacy; and
 - 6.5 college gratitude?
7. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the college students' subjective well – being when grouped according to:
 - 7.1 gender and
 - 7.2 Program/Degree?
8. Do the college students' adjustment significantly relate to the perceived stress and its subjective well – being?
9. What resilience in school environment uplift program may be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This portion presents the detailed methodology that will be utilized by the researchers in the study. The discussion focuses on the research design, the respondents of the study, sampling procedure, the instrument used in the study, the validation of instrument, the data gathering procedure and the statistical tool that will be utilized.

Research Design

This study employs descriptive – correlational research aims to provide static pictures of situations how one phenomenon is related to another in situation where the researcher has no control over the independent variables, the variables that believed to cause or influence the dependent or outcome variable through gathering data of surveys to establish the relationships between variables rather than to infer cause and effect relationship (Samosa & Dantay, 2022).

Population and Sample of the Study

The research utilized the purposive sampling technique which is a form of non-probability sampling where the sample group is targeted to have specific attributes. The sampling method used is highly accurate and relevant in the context of descriptive research. The respondents of this study are six hundred and two first year college students which were purposively chosen as the respondents of the study. They are regular students in their respective programs for the school year 2023-2024 in State University in Cavite.

Instrumentation

A researcher- made- checklist-survey questionnaire was used to gather data on the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being. This questionnaire has three (3) main portions.

Part I focuses on the college students' adjustment in terms of academic adjustment; social adjustment; personal adjustment; and institutional adjustment with five (5) indicators for each variable considered.

Part II focuses on the evaluation of the college students' perceived stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family- related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal-related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental- related stressor with five (5) indicators for each variables considered.

Part III focuses on the college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; academic grit; school connectedness; academic self-efficacy; and college gratitude stressor with five (5) indicators for each variables considered.

Validity and Reliability Test

To determine the validity of the research instrument which the researchers used and administered to the respondents, the checklist-survey questionnaire was presented to three (3) experts in the fields of psychology, guidance and counselling and research for the necessary correction, modification and to establish its content validity. Samosa and Dantay (2022) said that content validity chiefly targeting on the usefulness, originality, and representativeness of the items of the test to assess the characteristics to look for. This is usually done when a group of experts in the field of interest has inspected rigorously the test items.

Meanwhile, the final instrument used is from the result of the modifications or corrections made according to the suggestions or corrections done by the evaluators. Upon consideration of suggestions and recommendations given on face validity of the instrument, misleading questions were also modified.

After which, the researchers conducted a dry run or trial among twenty (20) nonrespondents with same characteristics of the subjects of the study for the test of reliability using Cronbach's Alpha Test of Validity and Reliability. All noted discrepancies or vague statements on the instrument were integrated and incorporated in the finalization of the instrument. Cronbach's Alpha is a measure of internal consistency that is calculated using sample variance, total scores, and number of items. Cronbach's Alpha is used to assess how consistently multiple items in a survey or test assess the same skill or characteristic. Higher values of Cronbach's alpha suggest higher internal consistency (Samosa et al, 2021).

Table 1. Face Validity of Survey Instruments

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
Clarity and Direction of Items	3.48	Highly Valid
Presentation and Organization of Items	3.60	Highly Valid
Suitability of Items	3.73	Highly Valid
Adequateness of the Content	3.87	Highly Valid
Attainment of the Purpose	3.93	Highly Valid
Objective	3.94	Highly Valid
Scale and Evaluation of Rating	3.78	Highly Valid
Overall	3.76	Highly Valid

Legend

Interval	Interpretation
3.28 – 4.00	Highly Valid
2.52 – 3.27	Valid
1.76 – 2.51	Less Valid
1.00 – 1.75	Not Valid at all

Table 2. Test of Validity and Reliability of Survey Instrument

Variables	Constructs	Validity		Reliability	
		V	Interpretation	α	Interpretation
College Students' adjustment	Academic adjustment	0.87	Very high	0.94	Excellent
	Social adjustment	0.89	Very high	0.93	Excellent
	Personal adjustment	0.92	Very high	0.92	Excellent
	Institutional adjustment	0.94	Very high	0.93	Excellent
	Overall	0.91	Very high	0.93	Excellent
College Students' Perceived Stress	Academic-related stressor	0.88	Very high	0.94	Excellent
	Time-related stressor	0.92	Very high	0.92	Excellent
	Family-related stressor	0.87	Very high	0.93	Excellent
	Financial-related stressor	0.92	Very high	0.91	Excellent
	Intrapersonal-related stressor	0.88	Very high	0.93	Excellent
	Interpersonal-related stressor	0.89	Very high	0.90	Excellent
	Teacher-related stressor	0.92	Very high	0.90	Excellent
	Environmental-related stressor	0.95	Very high	0.93	Excellent
Overall	0.90	Very High	0.92	Excellent	
College Students' Subjective Well – being	Satisfaction with Academics	0.91	Very high	0.90	Excellent
	Academic Grit	0.93	Very high	0.95	Excellent
	School Connectedness	0.89	Very high	0.93	Excellent
	Academic Self-Efficacy	0.92	Very high	0.92	Excellent
	College Gratitude	0.94	Very high	0.89	Excellent
Overall	0.92	Very High	0.92	Excellent	

Based on the test of validity shows that the instrument was established high validity and suitable for use because it has been fulfilled aspects of clarity and direction of items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of the content, attainment of the purpose, objective, scale, and evaluation of rating; the test of reliability of established excellent which was appropriate to be used to assess the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data from the study was using documentation procedure. This could be made possible by considering the details of the instruments. Upon the approval of the final draft of the instruments by the experts, the researchers wrote a letter to the Campus Administrator and the Director of Research and Extension for approval of the conduct of the research study. A notice to proceed were given. Upon the approval and endorsement of the study, the researchers sent letter to the target respondents for the conduct of the study. Then, the researchers facilitated survey questionnaire to the respondents of the study. Finally, was the collation and tabulation of data. The researchers collated, tallied code, and tabulated all the information acquired from the respondents of the study. Analysis and interpretation of statistical results followed.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure that the study will be conducted in an ethical way, the respondents of this study are aware of the topic. Their identities and answers remain confidential, and all devices used in the survey questionnaire are known by the respondents. The researchers consider the rights of the respondents in reporting the data. The researchers have

established the succeeding guidelines to ensure that all the informant's rights are upheld and protected (Samosa, 2020). The research objectives were presented to the respondents to aid them in a better understanding of the purpose of the study, and the survey. Thus, the written permission of the respondents asked for their agreement to participate in the study.

The devices used in collecting the data such as electronic google forms and paper-pencil survey questionnaires are known by the respondents. Hence, the collected data such as the surveys and reports will be made available to the respondents. Whereas rights of the respondents will be respected and considered foremost concerning the reporting of the data and lastly respondents' anonymity will lay with the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Data to be gathered from this study will be subjected to the following statistical treatments:

Percentage and Frequency distribution to describes the profile of the respondents in terms of age and programs/degree. This addressed the research question number 1.

Weighted Mean (WM) and Standard Deviation (SD) determine the evaluation of the respondents on the (1) college students' adjustment in terms of academic adjustment; social adjustment; personal adjustment; and institutional adjustment, (2) college students' perceived stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor, (3) college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; academic grit; school connectedness; academic self-efficacy; and college gratitude. This addressed research question numbers 2, 4 and 6.

T-test it measures the significant difference in the assessment of the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being when group according to their profiles in terms of gender and program/degree. This addressed research question numbers 3, 5 and 7.

Pearson r used to test the significant relationship between students' adjustment, perceived stress and its subjective well – being. This addressed research problem number 8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This portion discusses the data gathered from the procedures followed by the researchers. This includes presentation, analysis, interpretation, and organization of the results of the study. Data is presented in tabular forms supported with corresponding interpretation.

1. Profile of the Respondents

Presented on the succeeding tables were the distribution of the profile of six hundred two (602) college student- respondents in terms of gender and program or degree.

Table 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Female	363	60.3	1
Male	239	39.7	2
Total	602	100.0	

Shown on table 3 is the distribution of profile of college student- respondents when grouped according to gender. Based on the gathered data, it reflects that female college student - respondents were three hundred sixty – three (263) or sixty point - three percent (60.3 %) of the total respondents. In addition, male college student- respondents were two hundred thirty - nine (239) or thirty-nine point – seven percent (39.7%). From the data gathered, the researchers observed that majority of college student - respondents are female.

Dacuycuy and Dacuycuy (2019) stressed that female is more likely to be enrolled in college than male. It was supported by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2019) that, more female than male enrolled in undergraduate degrees in the State University.

Table 4. Profile of the respondents in terms of Program/Degree

Program	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Sciences	67	11.1	5
Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English	63	10.5	7
Bachelor of Science in Computer Science	111	18.4	1
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	94	15.6	3
Bachelor of Elementary Education	66	11.0	6
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	75	12.5	4
Bachelor of Science in Hotel & Restaurant Management	100	16.6	2
Bachelor of Science in Fisheries & Aquatic Science	26	4.3	8
Total	602	100.0	

Gleaned on table 4 is the distribution of college student- respondents when grouped according to academic programs/degree. Considering the gathered data, it reflects that that one – hundred eleven (111) or eighty – point – four percent (18,4%) of the college students – respondents were enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Computer Science. Meanwhile, one hundred (100) or sixteen – point – six percent (16.6%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Hotel & Restaurant Management. In a way, ninety – four (94) or fifteen – point – six percent (15.6%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Business Administration. In favor of seventy – five (75) or twelve – point – five percent

(12.5%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Information Technology. In request for sixty- seven (67) or eleven – point – one percent (11.1%) was enrolled in Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Sciences. Concomitantly, sixty – six (66) or eleven percent (11%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Elementary Education. Looking forward to sixty – three (63) or ten – point – five percent (10.5%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English. Lastly, twenty – six (26) or four – point – three percent (4.3%) were enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Fisheries & Aquatic Science. Noticeably, the gathered data the researchers observed that majority college student- respondents are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Computer Science.

These results confirmed that the computer science enrollment soars, powered by hot job market that opens so many doors and opportunities that dive into medicine, business, education, or any other sector due to changes in technology (in particular, the price and availability of hardware and software), changes in macroeconomic conditions that affect the demand for computer services, and changes in trade or immigration policies (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2018).

2. Assessment of the College Students' Adjustment

It can be gleaned on the table 5 was summary of the assessment of the college students' adjustment with five (5) variables considered includes the academic adjustment, social adjustment, personal adjustment, and institutional adjustment.

Table 5. Summary of the Assessment of the College Students' Adjustment

No	Variables	WM	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1	Academic adjustment	2.74	0.84	Adjusted
2	Social adjustment	2.93	0.03	Adjusted
3	Personal adjustment	2.70	0.04	Adjusted
4	Institutional adjustment	2.89	0.03	Adjusted
Overall		2.82	0.24	Observed

The data presented on the table, it shows that in terms of academic adjustment, the student – respondents' assessment on the factors and indicators set forth posed a weighted mean and standard deviation of 2.74 ± 0.84 and interpreted to be Adjusted. Taking aside, in terms of social adjustment, the student – respondents gained on the factors and indicators set forth posed a weighted mean and standard deviation of 2.93 ± 0.03 and interpreted to be Adjusted. Looking forward, student – respondents' evaluation on the personal adjustment yields gained on the factors and indicators set forth posed a weighted mean and standard deviation of 2.70 ± 0.04 and interpreted to be Adjusted. Cognizantly, in terms of institutional adjustments the student- respondents secured a weighted mean and standard deviation on the factors and indicators set forth of 2.89 ± 0.03 and interpreted to be Adjusted.

As such for, an over-all weighted mean and standard deviation for abovementioned variables were 2.82 ± 0.24 and interpreted to be Adjusted. The findings showed that the adjustment of students has been found to support student academic

success and social life (Alharthi, 2020). Individuals with a high level of psychological adjustment possess the ability to work normally during crises (Yıldırım, & Solmaz, 2020). High positive psychological adjustment has been linked to increasing satisfaction and quality of a student's life while reducing impediments associated with student depression, anxiety, stress and burnout (Roksa et al, 2021).

3. Test of Difference of Students' College Adjustment

Reflected on the table below is the analysis on the assessment of the student-respondents on the level of college students' adjustment when group according to gender. The test of inference to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents, the researchers employed the One-way ANOVA to compare the observations or measurements of the characteristic and draws decision as to whether there is a significant difference present among the sample means of the scores for every variable considered. Considerably, the conduct of the test of inference considered for the level of significance at 0.05, two-tailed with a degree of freedom (df) of 9 for each variable and degree of freedom of 39 for overall measures with the corresponding tabular F-value.

Table 6. Test of Difference of Students' College Adjustment when Group According Gender

No.	Variables	df	F-test value	F-test critical	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
1	Academic adjustment	9	.936	5.117	.362	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
2	Social adjustment	9	3.295	5.117	.107	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
3	Personal adjustment	9	.060	5.117	.812	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
4	Institutional adjustment	9	.419	5.117	.535	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
Overall		39	1.808	2.25	.187	Ho is Rejected	Not Significant

Gleaned on table 6 is the test of significant difference in the assessment of the student – respondents when group according to gender on the level of students' college adjustment in terms of academic adjustment, social adjustment, personal adjustment, and institutional adjustment. It shows that the gathered data for variable 1 “Academic adjustment” the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender reflects the computed F-value of .936 which is less than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 9, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender on the level of students' college adjustment in terms of academic adjustment.

In the analysis of the variable 2 “Social adjustment” assessment of the student-respondents when according to gender reflects the computed F-value of 3.295 which is less than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 9, this culled that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender on the level of students' college adjustment in terms of social adjustment.

Consequently, the variable 3 “Personal adjustment” the results of ANOVA obtained that the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender yields a computed F-value of .060 which is less than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 9, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender on the level of students’ college adjustment in terms of personal adjustment.

In quest for variable 4 “Institutional adjustment” the results showed that the computed F-value of .419 which is less than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 9, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender on the level of students’ college adjustment in terms of institutional adjustment.

Looking on the overall assessment of one- way ANOVA showed that that the computed F-value of 1.808 which is less than the F- test critical value of 2.25, at degree of freedom of 39, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents when according to gender on the level of students’ college adjustment.

The finding was contradicted to the stands of Ali et al, (2018) that there exist a significant difference in social adjustment of students with respect to gender; male students had better social adjustment than female students. The possible reason might be that the male students spend more time at university campus and have larger social circle. On the other hand, it was supported that the female and male students had no difference of academic adjustment. The reason for this might be that both male and female students are exposed to similar conditions of academic activities hence there was found no difference in their academic adjustment.

Test of Difference of Students’ College Adjustment when Group According Program/Degree

Reflected on the table below is the analysis on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of college students’ adjustment when group according to program/degree. The test of inference to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents, the researchers employed the One-way ANOVA to compare the observations or measurements of the characteristic and draws decision as to whether there is a significant difference present among the sample means of the scores for every variable considered. Considerably, the conduct of the test of inference considered for the level of significance at 0.05, two-tailed with a degree of freedom (df) of 39 for each variable and degree of freedom of 159 for overall measures with the corresponding tabular F-value.

Table 7. Test of Difference of Students' College Adjustment when Group According Program/Degree

No.	Variables	df	F-test value	F-test critical	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
1	Academic adjustment	39	1.060	2.25	.411	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
2	Social adjustment	39	2.237	2.25	.057	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
3	Personal adjustment	39	.982	2.25	.461	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
4	Institutional adjustment	39	1.069	2.25	.405	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
Overall		159	2.983	2.01	.006	Ho is Rejected	Significant

In the analysis of the student- respondents assessment on the level of students' college adjustment in terms of academic adjustment, social adjustment, personal adjustment, and institutional adjustment when according to program/degree gleaned the computed F-values of 1.060, 2.237, .982 and 1.069 respectively, which is less than the F- test critical value of 2.25, at degree of freedom of 39, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of students' college adjustment in terms of academic adjustment, social adjustment, personal adjustment, and institutional adjustment when according to when according to program/degree.

However, the overall assessment of one- way ANOVA showed that that the computed F-value of 2.983 which is greater than the F- test critical value of 2.01, at degree of freedom of 159, this reflects that the null hypothesis is rejected thus there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of students' college adjustment when group according to program/degree. It was supported with the findings of Maqbool et al (2021) degree/program of the students' differences were not observed in the level of college adjustment.

4. Assessment of the College Students' Perceived – Related Stress

It can be gleaned on the table 8 was summary of the assessment of the college students perceived – related stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor.

Table 8. Summary of the Assessment of the College Students' Perceived – Related Stress

No	Variables	WM	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1	Academic-related stressor	2.72	0.86	Stressed
2	Time-related stressor	2.70	0.86	Stressed
3	Family-related stressor	2.59	0.99	Stressed
4	Financial-related stressor	2.63	0.98	Stressed
5	Intrapersonal-related stressor	2.90	0.85	Stressed
6	Interpersonal-related stressor	2.82	0.87	Stressed
7	Teacher-related stressor	2.63	0.90	Stressed
8	Environmental-related stressor	2.33	0.64	Stressed
Overall		2.67	0.87	Stressed

In the analysis of the college students perceived – related stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor obtained a computed weighted means and standard deviation of 2.72 ± 0.86 , 2.70 ± 0.86 , 2.59 ± 0.99 , 2.63 ± 0.98 , 2.90 ± 0.85 , 2.82 ± 0.87 , 2.63 ± 0.90 , and 2.33 ± 0.64 respectively and interpreted to be stressed.

The overall weighted means and standard deviation of 2.67 ± 0.87 and interpreted to be stressed. College students are vulnerable to various stress inflicting situations which in turn tends them to be continually creative in managing stress feelings (Chandra, 2021). The stress producing factors among college students can arise from the subject or from the environment. These stressors are related to academic, socio-economic and personal successes in which the subject's failure to overcome leads to stress (Clabaugh, Duque, & Fields, 2021).

5. Test of Significant difference of Perceived Stress

Reflected on the table below is the analysis on the assessment of the student-respondents on the level of college students perceived stress when group according to gender. The test of inference to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents, the researchers employed the One-way ANOVA to compare the observations or measurements of the characteristic and draws decision as to whether there is a significant difference present among the sample means of the scores for every variable considered. Considerably, the conduct of the test of inference considered for the level of significance at 0.05, two-tailed with a degree of freedom (df) of 9 for each variable and degree of freedom of 79 for overall measures with the corresponding tabular F-value.

Table 9. Test of Significant difference of Perceived Stress when Group According Gender

No.	Variables	df	F-test value	F-test critical	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
1	Academic-related stressor	9	.431	5.117	.530	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
2	Time-related stressor	9	1.991	5.117	.196	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
3	Family-related stressor	9	.212	5.117	.658	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
4	Financial-related stressor	9	.887	5.117	.374	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
5	Intrapersonal-related stressor	9	.058	5.117	.815	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
6	Interpersonal-related stressor	9	.856	5.117	.382	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
7	Teacher-related stressor	9	1.765	5.117	.221	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
8	Environmental-related stressor	9	.464	5.117	.515	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
Overall		79	4.325	3.962	.041	Ho is rejected	Significant

In the analysis of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students perceived stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor when group according to gender gleaned the computed F-values of .431, 1.991, .212, .887, .058, .856, 1.765, and .464 respectively, which is less than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 9, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of college students perceived stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor when group according to gender.

However, the overall assessment of one- way ANOVA showed that that the computed F-value of 4.325 which is greater than the F- test critical value of 3.962, at degree of freedom of 79, this reflects that the null hypothesis is rejected thus there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of college students perceived stress when group according to gender.

Following the findings of Bhosale (2017) and Omoniyi and Ogunsanmi (2018), the present study showed that students' stress scores did not show statistically significant difference across their gender. However, it is also important to note that there are several studies which detected a significant difference in stress scores between males and female. For instance, Thawabieh and Qaisy (2020) presented that female students are more vulnerable to stress than males. This could be explained by the fact that females are more subjected to community pressure and they are still under the pressure of cultural

habits. On the other hand, Khan et al. (2020) found that male students are more stress than female students which might be due to the high standard parental and social expectations.

Test of Significant difference of Perceived Stress when Group According Program/Degree

Reflected on the table below is the analysis on the assessment of the student-respondents on the level of college students perceived stress when group according to program/degree. The test of inference to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents, the researchers employed the One-way ANOVA to compare the observations or measurements of the characteristic and draws decision as to whether there is a significant difference present among the sample means of the scores for every variable considered. Considerably, the conduct of the test of inference considered for the level of significance at 0.05, two-tailed with a degree of freedom (df) of 39 for each variable and degree of freedom of 319 for overall measures with the corresponding tabular F-value.

Table 10. Test of Significant difference of Perceived Stress when Group According Program/Degree

No.	Variables	df	F-test value	F-test critical	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
1	Academic-related stressor	39	.709	1.87	.664	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
2	Time-related stressor	39	1.998	1.87	.086	Ho is rejected	Significant
3	Family-related stressor	39	.812	1.87	.584	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
4	Financial-related stressor	39	.983	1.87	.461	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
5	Intrapersonal-related stressor	39	6.985	1.87	.000	Ho is rejected	Significant
6	Interpersonal-related stressor	39	1.835	1.87	.115	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
7	Teacher-related stressor	39	3.850	1.87	.004	Ho is rejected	Significant
8	Environmental-related stressor	39	6.722	1.87	.000	Ho is rejected	Significant
Overall		319	11.483	1.35	.000	Ho is Rejected	Significant

Considering the gathered data showed that the student-respondents assessment on the level of college students perceived stress in terms of academic-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; and interpersonal-related stressor when according to program/degree gleaned the computed F-values of .709, .812, .983, and 1.835 respectively, which is less than the F- test critical value of 1.87, at degree of freedom of 39, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student-respondents on the level of college students

perceived stress academic-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; and interpersonal-related stressor when according to program/degree.

However, the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students perceived stress in terms of time-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor showed that that the computed F-value of 1.998, 6.985, 3.850 and 6.722 respectively, which is greater than the F- test critical value of 1.87, at degree of freedom of 39, this reflects that the null hypothesis is rejected thus there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of college students perceived stress in terms of time-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor when group according to program/degree.

Furthermore, the overall assessment of one- way ANOVA showed that that the computed F-value of 11.483 which is greater than the F- test critical value of 1.35, at degree of freedom of 319, this reflects that the null hypothesis is rejected thus there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents on the level of college students perceived stress when group according to program/degree.

Ahmad et al, (2021) mentioned that academic overloads, course awkward, inadequate time to study, workload every semester, exams awkward, low motivation, and high family expectations were drive moderately stress among students where significantly differ when group according to degree/program.

6. College Students' Subjective Well – Being

It can be gleaned on the table 11 was summary of the assessment of the college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; academic grit; school connectedness; academic self-efficacy; and college gratitude.

Table 11. Summary of the Assessment of the College Students' Subjective Well – Being

No	Variables	WM	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1	Satisfaction with Academics	3.02	0.78	Satisfied
2	Academic Grit	2.90	0.77	Satisfied
3	School Connectedness	3.02	0.78	Satisfied
4	Academic Self-Efficacy	2.96	0.76	Satisfied
5	College Gratitude	3.19	0.84	Satisfied
	Overall	3.19	0.84	Satisfied

In the analysis of the college students perceived – related stress in terms of academic-related stressor; time-related stressor; family-related stressor; financial-related stressor; intrapersonal- related stressor; interpersonal-related stressor; teacher-related stressor; and environmental-related stressor obtained a computed weighted was 3.02,

2.90, 3.02, 2.96 and 3.19 respectively and interpreted to be stressed. The overall weighted means and standard deviation of 3.19 and interpreted to be stressed. Chattu et al (2020) stressed that subjective Well-being is essential for college students to succeed. Okoro et al. (2022) state that subjective well-being is intrinsically linked to students' quality of life among college students.

7. Test of Significant difference on the Assessment of the College Students' Subjective Well – Being

Reflected on the table below is the analysis on the assessment of the student-respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being when group according to gender. The test of inference to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents, the researchers employed the One-way ANOVA to compare the observations or measurements of the characteristic and draws decision as to whether there is a significant difference present among the sample means of the scores for every variable considered. Considerably, the conduct of the test of inference considered for the level of significance at 0.05, two-tailed with a degree of freedom (df) of 9 for each variable and degree of freedom of 49 for overall measures with the corresponding tabular F-value.

Table 12. Test of Significant difference on the Assessment of the College Students' Subjective Well – Being when Group According to Gender

No.	Variables	df	F-test value	F-test critical	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
1	Satisfaction with Academics	9	13.323	5.117	.006	Ho is Rejected	Significant
2	Academic Grit	9	2.566	5.117	.148	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
3	School Connectedness	9	.551	5.117	.479	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
4	Academic Self-Efficacy	9	10.760	5.117	.011	Ho is Rejected	Significant
5	College Gratitude	9	.172	5.117	.689	Ho is accepted	Not Significant
	Overall	49	4.833	4.038	.033	Ho is Rejected	Significant

Taking into consideration on the gathered data showed that the student-respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; and academic self-efficacy when group according to gender gleaned the computed F-values of 13.323, and 10.760 respectively, which is greater than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 9 this reflects that the null hypothesis is rejected thus there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; and academic self-efficacy when according to gender.

However, the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being in terms of academic grit; school connectedness; and college gratitude when according to gender. showed that that the computed F-value of 2.566, .551, 3.850 and .172 respectively, which is less than the F- test critical value of 5.117, at degree of freedom of 39, this reflects that the null hypothesis is accepted thus there is no significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being in terms of academic grit; school connectedness; and college gratitude when group according to gender. Overall, the One – way ANOVA test shows that there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being when group according to gender revealed on the computed F-value of 4.833 which is greater than the F- test critical value of 4.038, at degree of freedom of 49.

Tavakoly Sany et al, (2023) confirmed the results showed that gender had a significant effect on subjective well – being of the college students. In contrast to these studies, Coninck et al. (2019) and Cherepanov et al. (2020) insisted that gender affect subjective well – being among individuals.

Test of Significant difference on the Assessment of the College Students' Subjective Well – Being when Group According to Program/Degree

Table below is the analysis on the assessment of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being when group according to program/degree. The test of inference to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the respondents, the researchers employed the One-way ANOVA to compare the observations or measurements of the characteristic and draws decision as to whether there is a significant difference present among the sample means of the scores for every variable considered. Considerably, the conduct of the test of inference considered for the level of significance at 0.05, two-tailed with a degree of freedom (df) of 39 for each variable and degree of freedom of 199 for overall measures with the corresponding tabular F-value.

Table 13. Test of Significant difference on the Assessment of the College Students' Subjective Well – Being when Group According to Program/Degree

No.	Variables	df	F-test value	F-test critical	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
1	Satisfaction with Academics	39	9.631	1.87	.000	Ho is Rejected	Significant
2	Academic Grit	39	3.842	1.87	.004	Ho is Rejected	Significant
3	School Connectedness	39	3.389	1.87	.008	Ho is Rejected	Significant
4	Academic Self-Efficacy	39	9.880	1.87	.000	Ho is Rejected	Significant
5	College Gratitude	39	40.923	1.87	.000	Ho is Rejected	Significant
	Overall	199	11.370	1.35	.000	Ho is Rejected	Significant

The gathered data showed that the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; academic grit; school connectedness; academic self-efficacy; and college gratitude when group according to program/degree gleaned the computed F-values of 9.631, 3.842, 3.389, 9.880, and 40.923 respectively, which is greater than the F- test critical value of 1.87, at degree of freedom of 39 this reflects that the null hypothesis is rejected thus there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being in terms of satisfaction with academics; academic grit; school connectedness; academic self-efficacy; and college gratitude when according to program/degree. Overall analysis, one – way ANOVA test shows that there is significant difference on the assessment of the student- respondents assessment on the level of college students' subjective well – being when group according to program/degree revealed on the computed F-value of 11.370 which is greater than the F- test critical value of 1.35, at degree of freedom of 199.

Panicheva et al (2022) identified that subjective well – being of college students were differed when group according to areas of discipline belongs in the university.

8. Test of Relationship on the College Students' Adjustment, Perceived Stress and their Subjective Well – Being

Presented on the table 14 is the relationship between the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being. As shown on table 31, the two measures summarize the strength of a linear relationship in samples only. However, the researcher wants to draw conclusions about populations, not just samples, thus the need to conduct a hypothesis test or calculate a confidence interval will be utilized to test hypothesis for the population correlation to understand the linear association between the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being. Thus, presented are the Pearson relation in terms of the strength of correlation of the two variables and the t statistics to address the hypothesis.

Table 14. Test of Relationship on the College Students' Adjustment, Perceived Stress and their Subjective Well – Being

Variables		rx _y	Correlation	df	t-test computed	t-test critical	p-value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
College Adjustment	Perceived Stress	.75	Very strong	18	4.81	2.101	.00	Ho is accepted	Significant
College Adjustment	Subjective Well-Being	.83	Very strong	18	6.31	2.101	.00	Ho is rejected	Significant
Perceived Stress	Subjective Well-Being	.85	Very strong	23	7.74	2.069	.00	Ho is accepted	Significant

Considerably, based on the data gathered in terms of relationship between the college students' adjustment, and perceived stress computed r_{xy} value of 0.75 reflects a very strong positive correlation. Meanwhile, the significant relationship between college

students' adjustment, and perceived stress, the computed t-value of 4.81 far greater than the critical value of 2.101, the null hypothesis is rejected, thus there is a significant relationship between the college students' adjustment, and perceived stress. Hence, that very strong positive correlation indicates that, college students' adjustment, and perceived stress tend to go up in response to one another, the relationship is very strong positive correlation.

This confirmed the stands of the following studies of Bruffaerts et al., (2018); Hoyt et al., (2021); Tasso et al., (2021) that college students with greater perceived stress have poorer adjustment outcomes, such as a higher risk of mental health problems and lower academic engagement.

Looking on the test of relationship/association between college students' adjustment, and subjective well – being. It gleaned that the computed rxy value of 0.83 reflects a very strong positive correlation. As such, the significant relationship between college students' adjustment, and subjective well – being, the computed t-value of 6.31 far greater than the critical rxy value of 2.101, the null hypothesis is rejected, thus there is a significant relationship between college students' adjustment, and subjective well – being. Henceforth, that very strong positive correlation indicates that, college students' adjustment, and subjective well – tend to go up in response to one another, the relationship is very strong positive correlation. It was conformed with the findings of

Zhang et al, (2023) college adjustment is significantly correlated to subjective well-being in the students. Paramount to the results of the analysis using Pearson r comparison revealed that perceived stress has very strong positive correlation on their subjective well- being. As can be gleaned on rxy value .85. Further discussion showed that the comparison of the t- test value exceeds on the given tabular value, giving the researchers reason to reject the null hypothesis.

This may be safely to conclude that perceived stress correlate between subjective well- being. In effect, that very strong positive correlation indicates that, strong correlation on perceived stress and subjective well- being, tend to go up in response to one another, the relationship is very strong positive correlation.

It was aligned with the findings of Barbayannis et al, (2022) perceived stress in college is significantly correlated to subjective well-being in the students.

Conclusions

The respondents can be interpreted to have been experiencing psychological and adjustment problems in their college life. Moreover, perceived stress is also present. On the other hand, they are satisfied towards their college life as indicated by the findings of the study. This could denote that the school in a way balances the adjustments and stress of the students however, further investigation regarding the relationship between college adjustment and perceived stress to subjective well-being is recommended. It was identified that students' adjustment very strong correlated to perceived stress and their subjective well – being of the students.

Recommendations

Schools could capacitate students to adapt well facing the stresses they experience. Thus, the findings of this study are expected to form baseline information in constructing a guidance program to help students avoid if not, lessen the potential negative psychological effects of challenging experiences in their college life.

Consequently, more studies should be conducted to address this gap in research to help identify college students that may be disproportionately impacted by low adjustment, perceived high stress and low subjective well – being. From this, this research aims to evaluate the college students' adjustment, perceived stress and their subjective well – being. The results of the study will be the basis for crafting a guidance program which intends to capacitate students to adapt well when facing adversity or stress. This could help students avoid if not, lessen the potential negative psychological effects of challenging experiences.

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